

Impact Of Intellectual Potential On Performance With The Mediating Role Of Strategic Knowledge Management In The Telecommunication Sector Of Pakistan

Shah Zaib Sattar, Muhammad Majid Mahmood Bagram, Nadeem Ahmed Khan

Article Info

Article History

Received:
May 16, 2021

Accepted:
September 01, 2021

Keywords :

Intellectual Potential,
Strategic Knowledge
Management,
Organizational
Performance, Intellectual
Capital, Knowledge
Management

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5367270

Abstract

Purpose: The purpose of study was to analyze impact of intellectual potential of human capital on telecom companies of Pakistan with the mediating role of strategic knowledge management. The impact of intellectual potential has been tested on performance of telecom companies of Pakistan. It also tested mediating role strategic knowledge management between intellectual potential and organizational performance. *Methodology and Design:* Data was collected through online questionnaire from 150 employees of telecom companies in Pakistan. *Findings:* Findings of study supported the model as results showed that there are significant relationships among the variables.

Conclusion: The role of people has redefined due to Knowledge economy and many organizations have realized that employees are a valuable asset. Thus, the potentially competent managers have drastic impact on the strategic management of the organization by creating, developing and implementing policies, new ideas and practices that will improve the organizational performance.

Introduction

The beginning of the 21st Century has revealed new approaches and transformations to the definition of the organizational performance and to the economy. With the transformation, a new concept was emerged which was called "Knowledge economy" as a dynamic system of the organizational progress which confirms that the current economic development will not be based on the traditional methods and on material supply in the future, but on the latest knowledge and information. Knowledge regarding the economy was upheld as a key factor of future progress in 1990 by the policymakers. While the growth in cognitive demanding, well paid works compensation for the loss of skilled blue-collar jobs that had taken place in the age of globalization (Reich 1992; Giddens, 2013). As the phrase of knowledge economy was originated in 1960s and 1970s when the theorists of management took initiative to compare manual workers involved in physical labor for production of goods and services with the knowledge workers who were engaged in intellectual labor for generating ideas and information (Drucker, 1967; Bell, 1976). So, the progress of the human and knowledge into the economic activity appeared as the need for transformation of the cognitive process.

According to Soliman & Spooner (2000) some analysts considers the information technology as a key driver for knowledge management while many believe that knowledge management is about people not technology. Therefore, the importance of the human in the economic system requires the attention not only as a key element of the process of production and management but also prominent and powerful element that has huge potential for progress and development. Roos & Roos (1997) stated that human capital is the set of intangible assets that are implanted in the organizations.

This research paper study the impact of Intellectual potential on the performance of telecommunication sector in Pakistani companies with the mediating role of strategic knowledge management. Intellectual capital is one of the important factors in knowledge economy and researches has categorized it differently. But the main focus of this study is the Human capital because intellectual potential of humans referred to them who are a part of a firm, the knowledge these persons have commonly. Therefore, this study focused on the IP of the human capital and discarded the relation and structural capital. As Pulic (1998) defined that for value creation we need physical capital and intellectual potential in knowledge-based economy. He further elaborated that employees are the actual representor of the intellectual potential of any company as it is the ability of the employees doing their daily routine work for creating value. According to him there are two main differences between IC and IP. First, IC has been divided into human, structural and customer capital while neither structural nor customer capital could work without the employees. Second, IC indicated to be subjective but the calculations of IP are based on the real, objective market results and these are the points where the main difference exist. This suggests that these two components of

IC cannot be considered strictly as human aspects although they are generative activities of human being (Bontis, 1998).

Strategy is defined as the key factor in the capability of an organization because it gives guidance to the organization to complete its mission and achieve its vision by recognizing the conditions for creating competitive advantages (Lampaki&Papadakis, 2018). While intellectually potential employee has very effective impact on the strategic management of the organization as they have skill, knowledge and experience which can be transferred to the management planning through proper strategic management of any organization. Nowadays, managers seem to be very concerned with the adoption of proper knowledge management. That is why in this study, the strategic knowledge management is presented as a mediator that how it acts between the intellectual potential and organizational performance. On the other hand, it is also investigated that how the intellectual potential impacts the strategic knowledge management to affect the performance of any organization. Wu & Lin (2009), found positive correlation between organization knowledge and management strategy. They also found positive correlation between knowledge management strategy and knowledge management implementation. The actual objective of a strategy is the adoption of the roadmap which shows the interrelation between the organization knowledge and strategic management.

The knowledge management strategy has been categorized as knowledge source and knowledge focused in prior research. As Choi et al., (2008) has classified knowledge focused category into implicit and explicit oriented strategies. According to Zack (1999), in explicit oriented strategy the knowledge is transferred by codifying it through IT infrastructures and records while tacit knowledge is the exchange of knowledge by person to person contact. Moreover, Choi & Lee (2002) divided the knowledge source category into two types such as internal and external oriented strategy. In this study the main focus is on the internal and tacit oriented strategy as it is related to the skill, knowledge and experience of the workers who can share and transfer their knowledge through these strategies. Human capital considered as a strategic asset that can promote organizational strength to its core competitive advantage. Therefore, the management of IC has been well recognized as a strategic tool of organizations these days.

The telecommunication sector is one of the fastest developing sectors in Pakistan and the development of this industry is mainly based on perfectly competition and innovation which is due to the intellectual potential of the talented, skilled, competent, experienced and knowledgeable workers. Therefore, for this study the telecom sector has been selected to investigate its performance. As Nsour (2001) stated that technological advancement in communication technologies and computational power are converting the nature of knowledge, skills, talents and the expertise of the individuals. This transformation of knowledge has altered the requirement of worker. Now, global market demands a different type of worker with intellectual potential, approaches and competencies to systematic and critical thinking.

1.1 Problem statement:

In prior research, numerous studies have shown the impact of IC on OP and knowledge management (Sevibly; Edvinson; Stewart, 1997). But the existence of different approaches and categories of IC lead to the problem of the appropriate definition and management of IP. As intellectual potential is one of the important components of IC which is related to human potential. So, it is needed to obtain an idea regarding the link between intellectual potential of human capital with organizational performance and how that intellectual potential in workforce impacts the strategic management of the organizations to achieve goals. Moreover, there is not much information available in the literature about the treatment of the strategic knowledge management as a mediator. In this regard, the relationship of intellectual potential and perceived organization performance in the telecommunication sector required this study because in countries like Pakistan the sector of telecommunication need to know more about the contribution of the different factors which can impact on its performance. Wright et al., (1994) mentioned that the telecommunication industry plays a very crucial role in the progress of economic and social development of any country and he described it as an engine of the economic development in any country. As Pakistan telecom companies also need to efficiently and effectively use their knowledge management resources while taking more holistic approach to intellectual potential development.

Therefore, the present research paper investigates the impact of intellectual potential on the strategic knowledge management and performance of the telecom sector in Pakistan with the mediating role of strategic knowledge management.

1.2 Research Gap:

After studying the prior literature, it has been found that in the emerging knowledge-based perspective of the economy and business, the IP is the most important category which has been confused with intellectual capital (Pulic.,1998).The concept of IC which was presented by many researches (Stewart,1997; Sevible,1997) completely dominated by IC division into three parts: human, structural and customer capital but Pulic (1998) argues that neither structural nor customer capital can function without employees or human capital.

However main focus of the previous researches was on IC but not on the intellectual potential related to that human power. So, there was a gap to be filled by studying the impact of IP of human capital. Whereas, IC should be measured beyond the accounting methods. It might be good to move towards complementary methods of measuring IC and its components. As (Dumay,2009) stated that different methods of assessing IC within organizations should provide the chance to escape accountingisation. As Pulic (1998) has introduced VAIC method to measure IC and its components.

Therefore, Kianto et al., (2018) suggested that a comprehensive type of assessment permits the use of quantitative direction to define the inter-relationship of IC and its assets. While different models presented by (Kianto et al.,2014) related to possible interactions of the intellectual capital and its assets with Knowledge management practices. Which requires further study in different kinds of context. So, there is a need to study the Strategic knowledge management as a mediator between intellectual potential and organizational performance. The telecommunication sector is one of the fastest developing sectors in Pakistan. The development of this industry is mainly based on perfectly competition and innovation. This is the reason, why for this study the telecom sector has been selected to investigate its performance.

1.3 Research Questions:

Research Question 1: What is the relationship of intellectual potential and organizational performance?

Research Question 2: What is the relationship of Strategic Knowledge management and organizational performance?

Research Question 3: Does the strategic knowledge management mediate between the intellectual potential and organization performance?

1.4 Research Objectives:

Research Objective 1: To determine the impact of intellectual potential on strategic knowledge management.

Research Objective 2: To determine the impact of Intellectual potential on organizational performance.

Research Objective 3: To examine the mediating role of strategic knowledge management between Intellectual potential and the organizational performance.

1.5 Significance of the study:

This research paper has several important implications which can contribute not only on the theoretical grounds but also provide useful guidelines on practical grounds to the managers. On the theoretic grounds, the study is supportive in providing a model which shows relationship of IP and OP with the mediating role of SKM in telecom sector of Pakistan. While the practical contribution of this research are the findings of how IP is linked with the management of strategic knowledge in telecom sector. which will help to realize that the companies or organizations need to invest more in their potentially competent workforce. As IP is not related to the common workers or employee's knowledge and skills rather it is related to the highly skilled, educated, experienced and smart human power because such kind of human power have drastic impact on the performance of high-tech organizations like telecom industry. So, this research study can reveal the importance of IP on the strategic management.

1.6 Research Model:

1.7 Research Hypotheses:

H1: Intellectual Potential has the positive effect on Organizational Performance.

H2: Intellectual Potential has the positive effect on Strategic Knowledge Management.

H3: Strategic Management of Knowledge has the positive evocative outcome on Organizational Accomplishment.

H4: Strategic Knowledge Management has positively mediated between Intellectual Potential and Organizational Performance.

2. Methodology

2.1 Model of study:

Current research is quantitative where data collected from primary resources were analyzed. IP is an exogenous variable and OP is an endogenous variable while SKM is mediator.

2.2 Study Design:

The current study also comprises a field study as data was collected from different telecom companies. The primary data have been collected from telecom sector companies in Pakistan through online questionnaire while the study is a cross-sectional study.

2.3 Time Horizon:

The data in the current study is cross-sectional in nature and collected over an estimated time of two to three months and to complete study within a given time.

2.4 Unit of Analysis:

Unit of analysis defined the required degree from where data is gathered for analysis and measurement. In the present study, the paramount unit of measurement is workers of management level or in HRM.

2.5 Population:

The population of this present study is comprised of the workers of telecome in Pakistan. Since, telecom is a vast center for employment and innovation in Pakistan. This research was conducted from many cities of Pakistan. The target population of the consent was solicited during for feedback under a non-random basis to diminish common biasness, before giving the data to respondents, all the significant and necessary information was dispersed, and 150 questionnaires were distributed to reasonable sample size in a form of personal interaction and the cover letter under proper research.

2.6 Sampling Technique:

The purposive sampling technique used in this study due to limited time. The data was collected from 150 employees of telecom sector companies located in major cities of Pakistan. The SEM technique of SMART PLS has been used in this research.

2.7 Data Collection:

Through online research instrument that was in the form of questionnaires, I collected data to check the relationship of selected variables.

2.8 Response:

For collecting data through an online questionnaire, respondents were taken from all telecome companies. The minimum criteria of employment in such organization is graduation which revealed that respondents understand the English language and can easily fill the questionnaire. Thus, the questionnaire was not translated into local native language. Data collected from the employees of telecom companies that are located in different cities of Pakistan.

2.9 Scales and Measurement:

To fulfill the requirement of this study and data collection, the responses were collected through online questionnaires which were developed by different scholars in the previous studies. For Intellectual Potential, scale of 14-item was adopted based on previously used scale by Bontis et al., (1998). Strategic knowledge management (SKM) scale was adopted from Choi & Lee which is based on a five-item scale. (2003) for tacit knowledge and for internal oriented knowledge was adopted from Lee et al. (1999). For perceived organizational performance, the scale was adopted from Delaney & Huselid (1996).

The study used hypothesis testing to check the relationship between intellectual potential and the organizational performance with strategic knowledge management as a mediator. The questionnaires consisted of demographic variables such as respondent profile (gender, age, organization, city etc.). The questionnaire has been sub-divided into two sections A and B. (A) consisted of company and personal information that is based on ordinal and nominal scaling, while section (B) contained questions relating to Intellectual Potential, Strategic Knowledge management and the organizational performance. The responds were measured on 5point Likert scale which are 1=strongly disagree, 2=Disagree, 3=Neutral, 4=Agree, and 5=Strongly Agree.

2.10 Data Analysis:

Correlation and Regression Analysis by Smart PLS has been used for variations and correlations independent and dependent variables if any. The PLS has used as it ensures factor certainty by directly estimating potential variable scores, which is determined by introducing a flexible residual covariance structure, and most importantly, robust prediction of hierarchical models.

3. Hypothesis testing

3.1 Structural Equation Modeling:

SEM using PLS was performed to test the hypothesis including direct effect and indirect or mediating effect.

3.2 Direct Effect of IV-DV:

Figure 3.1 OP

Above diagram shows the direct effect of IV on DV. After applying the factor loading the regression analysis of IV on DV appeared which shows the beta value (β) 0.778 and R-square R^2 value 0.605.

3.3 Mediation Effect:

If both IV and mediator are positively related to DV then partial mediation is supported (BarronKenny ,1986; Hayes &Scharow, 2013). Hence, this study concludes partial mediation of strategic knowledge management between IP and OP.

Figure 3.2

Table 3 : Specific Indirect Effect

	Original mean	Sample mean	Standard deviation	t-statistics	p-value
IP-> SKM-> OP	0.210	0.208	0.106	1.987	0.047

The above table 4.7 shows that there is partial mediation exist as the P-value is 0.047 which is less than 0.05 and shows that indirect effect of mediation is found here while there is no total mediation. Because the existence of SKM as a mediator has not diminish the impact of IP on OP which is direct impact. Thus, the results depicted that H2, H3 and H4 are accepted because SKM has significant relationship with IP and OP.

Summary of results of testing hypothesis

Hypothesis	Statements	Results
H1	Intellectual potential has positive impact on Accepted Organizational performance.	Accepted
H2	Intellectual Potential has positive impact on strategic Accepted knowledge management.	Accepted
H3	Strategic knowledge management has positive impact on organizational performance.	Accepted
H4	Strategic knowledge management mediates between Accepted intellectual potential and organizational performance.	Accepted

4. Discussions

4.1 Intellectual Potential and Organizational performance:

The first hypothesis of this study predicted that Intellectual potential will positively influence the organizational performance and the findings of this study supports this hypothesis. Bozbura (2004) studied the relationship between the components of IC and market to book value ration. He concluded that human capital and relational capital have positive and significant relationship to market ratio. Zeghal&Maaloul (2010) studied the impact of IC on economic and financial performance of the companies in UK and the results of their study show that IC has a positive impact on the economic and financial performance of the companies. Furthermore, there is a significant association between IC and stock market performance but for high tech-companies.

Wang (2011) revealed that IC is positively related to market capitalization and return on assets. He further suggests that companies should focus on the delivery of internal information to achieve competitive advantage.

4.2 Intellectual Potential and Strategic knowledge management:

The second hypothesis of this study predicted that Intellectual potential will positively influence the strategic knowledge management and the findings of this study support this hypothesis. Skaggs Youndt (2004) find in their study that certain combinations of strategic positioning and human capital have strong relationship and result in superior performance. Kong & Thomson (2009) argues that IC, SHRM and HRM are closely related while IC play a key role in Strategic management of human resource. furthermore, they suggest that the strategic connections among these concepts required strong support to measure IC correctly. Because these are all interconnected.

4.3 Strategic Knowledge Management and Organizational performance:

The third hypothesis of this study predicted that strategic knowledge management positively influence the organizational performance and the findings of this study support this hypothesis. Filius et al., (2000) defined knowledge management in the organization as an assessment of the employee’s performance and as a discussion related to the organizational problems and failures, innovating new ideas into product development and learning. He further elaborated that strategic KM emphasis on alignment of knowledge strategy with organizational business and performance. In this context, it is oblivious that skilled and experienced employees create new and innovative ideas while support other employees to enhance and implement these new ideas in process development. Therefore, now organizations are involved in implementing the strategic knowledge management

to achieve and sustain competitive advantage for its performance. Abusweilem&Abualoush (2019) found a positive relationship between KM process and organizational performance in his study.

4.4 Strategic knowledge management mediates between IP and OP:

The fourth hypothesis of this study predicted that strategic knowledge management mediates between IP and OP. The results support the partial mediation of SKM between IP and OP. Hsu and Sabherwal (2011) suggest that KM capabilities mediate the impact of IC on firm performance. Specifically, their study of 533 Taiwanese publicly listed companies demonstrated that the impact of organizational capital and social capital on innovation was fully mediated by knowledge enhancement and knowledge utilization capabilities. Also, Chien and Chao (2011) found a mediating effect of cross-functional integration and co-production on IC and sale performance. George & Venkatapathy (2018) examined the role of KM as mediator in the relationship between spiritual intelligence and employee engagement in information services industry. The results showed that KM is a mediator between spiritual intelligence and employ engagement and it is also noted that complete mediation exists between these constructs. Barkat&Beh (2018) conducted a research to test potential effect of IC in a developing country. While the main objective of this study is to test the mediation effect of knowledge process capability between intellectual capital and organizational performance. The results revealed that knowledge process capability mediates between intellectual capital and organizational performance.

4.5 Implications:

4.5.1. Theoretical and practical implications:

This study has some important implications for theory as well. As theoretically it has been discussed in many studies and empirically proven that individuals who are skilled, experienced, competent and knowledgeable have positive impact on performance of any organizations. Moreover, there is a little literature available about the SKM as a mediator but this study added that SKM can be partially mediated between IP and OP.

This study not only added in the theory but also provide practical implications as well. Managers can use the findings of this study to introduce the strategies which can enhance the organizational performance if they are skilled, experienced and competent since these are the abilities of intellectually potential employees. As this IP model will allow more detailed knowledge of strategic management which is going to help the managers in their task of valuing and increasing activity and efficiency. The findings of this study encourage the decisions makers and HR executive officers to implement more comprehensive strategies by taking intellectual potential of the employees into consideration at the organizational level. Furthermore, it is suggested that executives and other decision makers regard the intellectual potential as an investment which is capable of yielding long term competitive advantage for organizational performance. The practical implications will not only help the managers or decision makers of the private sectors but also help the policy makers of public sectors. As in this emerging knowledge management paradigm, intangible values and knowledge has become the main source of competitive advantage for organizational performance either related to private sector or public. Since public sector are facing tough performance challenges and if these elements are managed properly, will ensure the success in public sector too. Hence, there is relatively little methods are introduced related to strategic management of KM in perspective of IP, the proposed model can help the policy makers to value the selection of potentially competent people.

4.6 Limitations and Directions for future research work:

Future studies can test the relationships proposed in this study with longitudinal design as the current study design was cross-sectional. This study focused on telecom sector only but another sector such as banking and pharmacy can be tested. Future studies can also test the mediating impact of various other constructs such as innovation impact. Since in the current study, private sector was tested but for future studies, the proposed relationship can be checked with public sector performance as well.

4.7 Conclusion:

It has been argued that human capital was not paid much attention in the role of competitive advantage of business in knowledge economy. Whereas, the early literature about knowledge management focused on the technological issues. However, the importance of people management yet to be fully developed. According to Soliman& Spooner (2000) some analysts considers the information technology as a key driver for knowledge management while many believe that knowledge management is about people not technology.

Since the main focus of this paper on IP of HC and SKM not on other assets of IC. Thus, a competent individual is the key in a company's effort to realize and develop its business ideas (Sveiby ,1990; Hansson, 2001). Rastogi (2003) stated that the collective efforts of highly competent, skilled, capable, creative, motivated and well-informed people play a significant role in creating and delivering a competitively superior value to its firm. The

current study also provided a positive relationship among all variables of the model. Therefore, it has been proved that intellectual potential can play a significant role in increasing the organizational performance of telecom companies. Moreover, strategy can significantly mediate between IP and OP. IP is one of the most important sources for sustainable competitive advantage in the companies whereas an important managerial responsibility is to manage and utilize the potential of the company in a better way. The growth and decline in the intellectual resources actually point towards the intellectual performance of the company. The crux is that it is individuals not the company that own and control the topmost source of the competitive advantage. This is called the knowledge of organizational members. This is why the concepts like hidden assets, intangible resources or intellectual potential often reveal more about the future earning capabilities of a company than any of the conventional performance.

References

- Abusweilem, M., &Abualoush, S. (2019). The impact of knowledge management process and business intelligence on organizational performance. *Management Science Letters*, 9(12), 2143-2156.
- Barkat, W., &Beh, L. S. (2018). Impact of intellectual capital on organizational performance: evidence from a developing country. *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*, 17(2), 1-8.
- Bell, D. (1976, May). The coming of the post-industrial society. In *The Educational Forum* (Vol. 40, No. 4, pp. 574-579). Taylor & Francis Group.
- Bell, E., Bryman, A., & Harley, B. (2018). *Business research methods*. Oxford university press.
- Bontis, N. (1998). Intellectual capital: an exploratory study that develops measures and models. *Management decision*.
- Bozbura, F. T. (2004). Measurement and application of intellectual capital in Turkey. *The learning organization*.
- Chien, S. H., & Chao, M. C. (2011). Intellectual capital and new product sale performance of the financial services industry in Taiwan. *The Service Industries Journal*, 31(16), 2641-2659.
- Choi, B., & Lee, H. (2002). Knowledge management strategy and its link to knowledge creation process. *Expert Systems with applications*, 23(3), 173-187.
- de Jong, J. A., &Roelofs, E. C. (2000). Knowledge management in the HRD office: a comparison of three cases. *Journal of Workplace Learning*.
- Delaney, J. T., &Huselid, M. A. (1996). The impact of human resource management practices on perceptions of organizational performance. *Academy of Management journal*, 39(4), 949-969.
- Drucker, P. F. (1967). *The Effective Executive*.
- Dumay, J. C. (2009). Intellectual capital measurement: a critical approach. *Journal of intellectual capital*.
- Edvinsson, L., & Malone, M. (1997). *Realizing your company's true value by finding its hidden brain power*. Intellectual Capital.
- George, M. G., &Venkatapathy, R. (2018). Mediating effect of knowledge management on spiritual intelligence and employee engagement. *International Review of Management and Business Research*, 7(3), 685-698.
- Giddens, A. (2013). *Europe in the global age*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Hsu, I. C., &Sabherwal, R. (2011). From intellectual capital to firm performance: the mediating role of knowledge management capabilities. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, 58(4), 626-642.
- Kianto, A., &Andreeva, T. (2014). Knowledge management practices and results in service- oriented versus product-oriented companies. *Knowledge and Process Management*, 21(4), 221-230.
- Kianto, A., Ritala, P., Vanhala, M., &Hussinki, H. (2018). Reflections on the criteria for the sound measurement of intellectual capital: A knowledge-based perspective. *Critical Perspectives on accounting*, 102046.
- Kong, E. (2010). Intellectual capital and non-profit organizations in the knowledge economy. *Journal of Intellectual capital*.
- Lampaki, A., &Papadakis, V. (2018). The impact of organizational politics and trust in the top management team on strategic decision implementation success: A middle-manager's perspective. *European Management Journal*, 36(5), 627-637.
- Nsour, M. (2001), "Developing A Strategic Approach to Intellectual Capital Development in the Arab States", UNDP/RBAS Terms of Reference Paper, New York, NY.
- Pulic, A. (1998). *Measuring the Performance of Intellectual Potential in Knowledge Economy* (presented in 1998 at the 2nd McMaster World Congress on Measuring and Managing Intellectual Capital by the Austrian Team for Intellectual Potential).
- Rastogi, P. N. (2003). The nature and role of IC: Rethinking the process of value creation and sustained enterprise growth. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 4(2), 227-248
- Reich, R. B. (1992). *The Work of Nations: Preparing Ourselves for 21st Century Capitalism*.
- Roos, G., &Roos, J. (1997). Measuring your company's intellectual performance. *Long range planning*, 30(3), 413-426

- Skaggs, b., & Youndt, m. (2004). Strategic positioning, human capital and performance in service organizations: a customer integration approach.
- Soliman, F., & Spooner, K. (2000). Strategies for implementing knowledge management: role of human resources management. *Journal of knowledge management*.
- Stewart, T., & Capital, I. (1997). *The new wealth of organizations*. Nicholas Brealey, London.
- Sveiby, K. E. (1997). *The new organizational wealth: Managing & measuring knowledge-based assets*. Berrett-Koehler Publishers.
Vintage.
- Wang, M. (2011). Measuring intellectual capital and its effect on financial performance: Evidence from the capital market in Taiwan. *Frontiers of Business Research in China*, 5(2), 243-265.
- Wright, P. M., McMahan, G. C., & McWilliams, A. (1994). Human resources and sustained competitive advantage: a resource-based perspective. *International journal of human resource management*, 5(2), 301-326.
- Wu, I., & Lin, H. (2009). A strategy-based process for implementing knowledge management: an integrative view and empirical study. *Journal of American Society for Information and Technology*, 60(4), 789–802.
- Zack, M. H. (1999). Developing a knowledge strategy. *California Management Review*, 41(3), 125–145.
- Zeghal, D., & Maaloul, A. (2010). Analyzing value added as an indicator of intellectual capital and its consequences on company performance. *Journal of Intellectual capital*.

Author Information

Shah Zaib Sattar

M.Phil Business Economics, Pakistan Institute of
Development Economics, Islamabad, Pakistan

Dr. Muhammad Majid Mahmood Bagram

(Corresponding Author)
Associate Professor, Department of Business
Administration, Allama Iqbal Open University,
Islamabad, Pakistan

Dr. Nadeem Ahmed Khan

Assistant Professor, Pakistan Institute of
Development Economics, Islamabad, Pakistan
